

A comparative study of homogeneous and heterogeneous photo-Fenton process for degradation of highly chlorinated aromatic solvent at near neutral pH using a visible LED light as radiation source.

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The efficiencies of homogeneous (PF-HO) and heterogeneous (PF-HE) photo-Fenton oxidation process were compared for the degradation of a highly chlorinated aromatic solvent, 1,2,4-trichlorobenzene (124-TCB), using a Vis-LED as radiation source for natural pH conditions. Here, two parameters were quantified: 1) use of incident radiation, expressed in terms of photonic degradation efficiencies (moles of pollutant converted by moles of photons incident on the reactor surface); 2) utilization of reagents, expressed in terms of the specific consumption of oxidizing agent during the degradation reaction (mass of HP consumed per mass of contaminant converted). For both reactant systems, conversions of 124-TCB after 180 min of reaction ($X_{124-TCB}^{180}$) higher than 45% were obtained. However, to obtain $X_{124-TCB}^{180}$ greater than 90%, the PF-HE system required at least 360 min of reaction. While the PF-HO system obtained these conversions in only 180 min of reaction (for many reactive conditions).

Introduction

The occurrence of chlorinated organic compounds (COCs) in the aqueous environment has become an emerging public and scientific concern due to their potential adverse impacts on biota and human health. By the EU Water Framework Directive (Directive 2000/60/EC), several COCs have been added in the last two decades to the list of substances to be monitored, encouraging limiting their production and use.

Technologies leading to complete COCs degradation need to be developed. At this point and considering the low biodegradability and high persistence of these compounds, several chemical technologies have been proposed for their abatement, including advanced oxidation processes (AOPs). Photo-Fenton oxidation, based on the use of hydrogen peroxide (HP) and an iron (Fe) catalyst under irradiation by UV-light, is an AOPs that has been used for the efficient degradation of a wide range of organic compounds, including many COCs. Based on the catalyst used in the system (i.e., free/complexes iron ions or iron-based solid catalysts), the photo-Fenton reaction could be classified as homogeneous (PF-HO) or heterogeneous (PF-HE) processes [1].

The major disadvantages of the PF-HO process are sludge generation, limited pH range, high iron discharge to the environment, and difficulty in iron ion recovery. In the PF-HE system, the main disadvantage is found in the

mass transfer limitations of the reactants towards the active catalyst centres (generation of hydroxyl radicals). Furthermore, as it is a dispersive medium, the radiant energy required to achieve efficient activation of the system is usually considerably higher than the required for homogeneous processes. Thus resulting in pollutant degradation rates considerably lower than those obtained in the homogeneous process. However, the main advantages of a heterogeneous process are less or null iron leaching, environment friendly, and easy separation of the catalyst from the medium, and the possibility of making multiple uses of it.

In this work, 1,2,4-trichlorobenzene (124-TCB) was selected as a model compound to study its abatement using the PF-HO (ferrioxalate as iron source) and PF-HE (goethite as iron source) processes at neutral pH conditions. As the radiation source, a visible monochromatic light-emitting diode (LED) light (470 nm) was used.

To evaluate the operational efficiency of both reactant systems, two parameters were quantified: 1) use of incident radiation, expressed in terms of photonic degradation efficiencies (moles of pollutant converted by moles of photons incident on the reactor surface); 2) utilization of reagents, expressed in terms of the specific consumption of oxidizing agent during the degradation reaction (mass of HP consumed per mass of contaminant converted) [2]. Note that both parameters are

representative of the overall behaviour of the system since not only considering the conversion levels obtained for the pollutant but are also indicative of the operating cost of these processes (radiant energy and hydrogen peroxide usage). Besides, and for the evaluation of these operational parameters, different catalyst and oxidizing agent concentrations were used for many levels of incident radiation.

Material and Methods

The experiments were carried out in a cylindrical borosilicate thermostated batch reactor ($T=25\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$; $V_T=0.1\text{ L}$). The radiation source, a monochromatic LED lamp (470 nm), with an optical power output of up to 4.17 W, generates a collimated beam over the reactor windows of 11 cm^2 . This power could be adjusted using a LED controller.

The role of the LED light in the processes is to enhance the redox cycle of "Fe (III)" to "Fe (II)" in the PF-HO and PF-HE reactions. Preliminary tests have shown that goethite has the lowest transmittance (maximum absorbance) for wavelength lower than 500 nm [3]. On the other hand, considering the energy gap presented by goethite (2.2 eV), a photon with a wavelength less than 470 nm will have enough energy (2.6 eV) to overcome this forbidden energy barrier, producing the photo-activation of the solid. Furthermore, for these wavelengths, the iron-oxalate system presents high molar extinction coefficients even for low iron concentrations [4]. In this way, the wavelength of the lamp source was selected as 470 nm. All irradiance measurements (I, Wcm^{-2}) were performed with a UV-VIS spectrometer FLAME UV-Vis coupled with an optical fiber.

To simulate the contaminated water, 124-TCB was added to a ferrioxalate solution (PF-HO) or mili-Q water (PF-HE). These solutions saturation were carried out under controlled temperature and agitation conditions (124-TCB saturation concentration, 28 ppm).

The organic compounds concentration in reaction samples were identified and quantified by Gas Chromatography (Agilent 6890N, Santa Clara, CA, USA) with a Mass Spectrometry Detector (GC/MS). Here a standard internal compound (bicyclohexyl) was used for pollutant quantification. The concentration of HP and Fe were determined by colorimetric titration, using a spectrophotometer at 410 and 510 nm, respectively (BOECO S-20 UV-VIS, Hamburg, Germany).

Ionic organic by-products, such as carboxylic acids and chlorides, were measured by Ion Chromatography (Metrohm 761 Compact IC, Gallen, Suiza). The pH was measured with a Basic 20-CRISON pH electrode. For all PF-HE tests, Goethite (Sigma-Aldrich) used was

compounded by 57.3 wt % of Fe (III), with a specific surface area (SBET) of $10.24\text{ m}^2\text{g}^{-1}$ [3].

Microtox Model 500 Toxicity Analyser (Strategic Diagnostic Inc.) was used in order to carry out the acute bioluminescence assay (*Vibrio fischeri* bacteria) and evaluate the toxicity of the samples during the PF-HO and PF-HE process.

The collected sample (4mL) was filtered (once the goethite was removed from the reaction sample) and extracted with 0.8 mL of n-hexane. The mixture of both phases was shaken for 2 min followed by 10 min of settlement, allowing the organic phase separation by decantation. More details of the experimental device and the analytical techniques used can be found in Lorenzo et al., 2021 [3].

The key process parameters studied for the PF-HO and PF-HE process were HP concentration, 61.50 to 612 ppm; Rad level, 0.1 to 0.24 Wcm^{-2} ; Fe concentration, 3 to 10 ppm for the PF-HO, and 0.1 to 1 gL^{-1} goethite for the PF-HE. Note, that for all PF-HO tests, an Oxalate/Fe molar ratio of 10 was used (oxalate excess) to reduce the iron precipitation [4].

Results and Discussion

First, it should be noted that the degradation rates of the pollutant were considerably higher in the PF-HO system compared to the PF-HE one (all conditions tested). For both reactant systems, conversions of 124-TCB after 180 min of reaction ($X_{124-TCB}^{180}$) higher than 45% were obtained. However, to obtain $X_{124-TCB}^{180}$ greater than 90%, the PF-HE system required at least 360 min of reaction. While the PF-HO system obtained these conversions in only 180 min of reaction (for many reactive conditions).

To evaluate and compare the photochemical behaviour of the studied process, the photonic efficiency was calculated. It is defined as "the ratio of the number of reactant molecules degraded during a given time, to the total number of photons arrived at the reactor wall, during the same period" (see Eq. 1):

$$\phi_{124-TCB}^t = \left(C_{124-TCB}^{i0} - C_{124-TCB}^{if} \right) V_T / q_w A_w (t_f - t_0) \quad \text{Eq. 1}$$

here $\phi_{124-TCB}^t$ is the photonic efficiency of 124-TCB degradation (molEins^{-1}), $C_{124-TCB}^{i0}$ and $C_{124-TCB}^{if}$ are 124-TCB concentrations at initial and final time (t_0 and t_f), respectively, (molL^{-1}), V_T the total volume of reaction (L), q_w the net radiation flux at the reactor wall ($\text{Einscm}^{-2}\text{s}^{-1}$) and A_w , the irradiated area (cm^2).

The higher photonic efficiencies were observed in the PF-HO system. For conditions of maximum $X_{124-TCB}^{180}$ in the PF-HE system ($I = 0.24\text{ W}$, $\text{Cat} = 0.1\text{ g L}^{-1}$ and $\text{HP} = 612\text{ ppm}$, $X_{124-TCB}^{180} = 65\%$), the $\phi_{124-TCB}^{180} = 9.8 \times 10^{-4}\text{ molEins}^{-1}$ was 15 times lower than the minimum values obtained in the PF-HO system

($\phi_{124-TCB}^{180} = 1.6 \times 10^{-2} \text{ molEins}^{-1}$, $l=0.1 \text{ Wcm}^2$, $\text{Fe}=10$ ppm, $\text{HP}=612$ ppm, $X_{124-TCB}^{180} = 86\%$). Furthermore, the $X_{124-TCB}^{180}$ obtained for these P-HO and PF-HE experimental conditions is 32% higher (86% vs 65%, see Graphical Abstract). For heterogeneous conditions, the maximum $\phi_{124-TCB}^{180}$ are obtained for low Rad intensities ($l=0.1 \text{ Wcm}^2$) and low/medium catalyst loads (Cat=0.1 and 0.5 gL^{-1}). In these conditions, the scattering out of the system was minimized. However, the pollutant conversions obtained are not lower (in the order of 50 and 70% for 180 and 360 min of operation respectively). As a disadvantage the PF-HO system requires the addition of a chelating agent (oxalate) to keep the iron in solution (pH=7) and obtain high molar extinction coefficients. This produces an additional carbon load to the system. For an Oxalate/Fe molar ratio of 10, the TOC supplied to the system can be up to 43 ppm (this for 10 ppm Fe). This value being 3.75 times higher than the TOC contributed by the pollutant (28 ppm 124-TCB).

Additionally, the specific consumption of the oxidizing agent ($\gamma_{HP/124-TCB}^t$) is a useful parameter to evaluate the consumption of the main economical reagent (HP) of these processes. It is defined as "the ratio of the oxidant agent mass-consumed during a given reaction time, to the mass of contaminant converted, during the same time" (see Eq. 2):

$$\gamma_{HP/124-TCB}^t = \left(C_{HP}^{t0} - C_{HP}^{tf} \right) / \left(C_{124-TCB}^{t0} - C_{124-TCB}^{tf} \right) \quad \text{Eq. 2}$$

Conclusions

First, it should be noted that the degradation rates of the pollutant were considerably higher in the PF-HO system compared to the PF-HE one (all conditions tested). Being necessary longer reaction times in the PF-HE system (180 min vs 360 min) to obtain 124-TCB conversions higher than 90%. Maximum $\phi_{124-TCB}^{180}$ were obtained for the PF-HO process (high levels of radiation scattering for the PF-HE system). However, the addition of a chelating agent (oxalate) to keep the iron in solution (pH=7) and obtain high molar extinction coefficients (470 nm) was necessary for these conditions (additional carbon load to the system). On the other hand, a better use of the HP reagent in the heterogeneous system is obtained (considerably lower $\gamma_{HP/124-TCB}^{180 \text{ min}}$).

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For the entire range of operating conditions evaluated, the $\gamma_{HP/124-TCB}^{180 \text{ min}}$ obtained for the PF-HE system were considerably lower than those obtained for the PF-HO one. Under conditions of maximum conversion of the pollutant, the PF-HO system ($X_{124-TCB}^{180} = 96\%$, $l=0.18 \text{ Wcm}^2$, $\text{Fe}=5$ ppm, $\text{HP}=305$ ppm) showed a $\gamma_{HP/124-TCB}^{180 \text{ min}}$ 2.6 times higher (4.75 mg HP/ mg 124-TCB vs 1.82 mg HP/ mg 124-TCB) than the consumption observed for maximum pollutant conversions in the PF-HE system ($X_{124-TCB}^{180} = 65\%$, $l=0.24 \text{ Wcm}^2$, Cat=0.1 gL^{-1} and 612 ppm HP, see Graphical Abstract). Furthermore, for these conditions, the PF-HE system reached a $X_{124-TCB}^{360 \text{ min}} = 90\%$, with $\gamma_{HP/124-TCB}^{360 \text{ min}}$ of 2.19 mg 124-TCB/mg HP (still minor to that presented in the homogeneous system). Therefore, a better use of the HP reagent in the heterogeneous system was obtained. Complementary studies are being carried out in order to quantify the reduction in toxicity levels (Microtox) obtained in both systems (PF-HO and PF-HE). At this point, traces of toxic reaction intermediates (mainly chlorobenzenes and chlorophenols) have been detected.

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HACE CONSTAR QUE:

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Presentaron la ponencia oral titulada:

A comparative study of homogeneous and heterogeneous photo-Fenton process for degradation of highly chlorinated aromatic solvent at near neutral pH using a visible LED light as radiation source.

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